

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

EDGE AI ACCELERATION TECHNIQUES FOR REAL-TIME IMAGE PROCESSING IN EMBEDDED SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The article discusses the possible ways of accelerating Edge AI real-time image processing on embedded systems with limited computational and energy resources. The concentration is on machine vision, especially object recognition, and three platforms are examined: ESP32-Wrover-Dev v1.6, Sipeed Maix Bit, and NVIDIA Jetson TX2 DevKit.

The ESP32 failed to gather enough power for full on-board AI processing, thus server-based recognition became necessary. The Sipeed Maix Bit, running the YOLOv2 model, was fairly successful, but the problems were in limiting the types of models and their accuracy over the distance. The NVIDIA Jetson TX2 with the models of SSD Inception V2, Peoplenet, and Peoplenet-Pruned tested by the Prestigio PWC420 HD camera and the Samsung Galaxy A54 camera was able to provide the highest recognition rates. Peoplenet gave the best results across the board, while Peoplenet-Pruned achieved similar accuracy with half the resource consumption. SSD Inception V2, however, appeared to behave erratically and perform poorly on longer distances or low-light conditions.

The results suggest that for high-accuracy, real-time people detection on embedded systems, NVIDIA Jetson TX2 with the Peoplenet or Peoplenet-Pruned is the best choice, whereas lightweight platforms, such as the Sipeed Maix Bit, tend to be more consistent under varying light conditions yet less accurate for long-distance scenarios. The study highlights the compromises between performance and the consumption of resources versus conditions when realizing AI at the edge.

Keywords: Edge AI, embedded systems, machine vision, object recognition, AI acceleration.

1. Introduction

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into embedded devices is a relevant and rapidly developing area in modern technologies. Since embedded platforms are already widespread at the moment, their modernization is becoming increasingly relevant. One of the most effective ways to improve such systems is to integrate AI into these systems [1].

Since there are various AI algorithms designed to perform various types of tasks, the area for studying this area is quite extensive [2]. This article considers a part of AI called machine or computer vision [3, 4].

Integrating an AI system into a platform with limited resources is a complex task. The recognition process, depending on the required speed and accuracy, is computationally and energy intensive [5].

Modern algorithms allow saving the resources necessary for work, but, unfortunately, to a degree not sufficient for their correct and uninterrupted operation on embedded systems.

Despite the complexity, the integration of AI systems on platforms with limited resources remains a pressing issue. To solve it, special optimization and compression algorithms for existing machine vision systems were developed, including optimized models for object recognition. [6]. Unfortunately, it is extremely difficult to achieve smaller volumes and higher speeds with the same accuracy parameters. Therefore,

the recognition quality of lightweight models is, on average, lower.

This means that by applying such algorithms [7], it becomes possible to place sufficiently accurate and fast machine vision systems on embedded devices [8].

This article is devoted to testing such systems on various embedded systems in various conditions with the practical goal of implementing the most suitable system into an existing project.

2. Description of devices for object recognition

In the previously described work, a study of machine vision methods on embedded systems using modern microcontrollers was conducted [9]. In order to compare the capabilities and performance of embedded platforms, the following devices were used: ESP32-Wrover-Dev v1.6 (ESP32-Wrover-E), Sipeed Maix Bit, and Nvidia Jetson TX2 DevKit.

For each platform, specialized models were developed that allow recognizing objects relevant to the research tasks, such as people or faces. In these models, recognized objects of the corresponding type were designated by the identifiers “person” and “face”.

2.1. ESP32-Wrover-DEV v1.6 (ESP32-Wrover-E)

The embedded system ESP32-Wrover-DEV v1.6 (ESP32-Wrover-E), hereinafter ESP32, was created as a universal module supporting Wi-Fi, Bluetooth and Bluetooth LE MCU technologies.

The parameters of the ESP32 are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

ESP32 Parameters

Part of the module	Description
1	2
CPU	Two low-power Xtensa® 32-bit LX6 microprocessors
GPU	-
Memory	448 KB of ROM for booting and core functions. 520 KB of on-chip SRAM for data and instructions. 8 KB of SRAM in RTC, which is called RTC FAST Memory and can be used for data storage 8 KB of SRAM in RTC, which is called RTC SLOW Memory 1Kbit of eFuse 8 Mb PSRAM
Storage	4 MB SPI flash memory
Screen	-
Camera	OV2640
TF card slot	-

Source: Compiled by the author.

To enable machine vision on this embedded system, various tools are used, such as OpenCV and TensorFlow. It should be noted that the computing power of the ESP32 is not enough to run a full-fledged TensorFlow framework. There are special converters that allow you to create a lightweight TensorFlow Lite framework. The current project used the OpenCV library with a pre-trained YOLOv3 model [10, 11].

This module will not participate in the final tests, since the results that at least somewhat meet the requirements were not obtained, namely, it was not possible to launch the system running entirely on the ESP32. The part located on the module, when using the

OpenCV library, takes a frame and places it on the server, which is located on the same module. Processing and recognition is performed by a computer connected to the module's server.

2. 2. Sipeed Maix Bit

Sipeed Maix Bit is one of the families of devices aimed at the "AI at the edge" market. This module provides high performance with low physical and energy costs, allowing the implementation of high-precision artificial intelligence of the "AI at the edge" category.

The parameters of Sipeed Maix Bit are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Sipeed Maix Bit Parameters

Part of the module	Description
1	2
CPU	Dual-core 64bit RISC-V/400MHz (double precision FPU integration)
GPU	-
Memory	8MiB 64bit on-chip SRAM
Storage	16MiB Flash, support micro SDXC expansion storage (max 128GB)
Screen	2.4 inch TFT, screen resolution: 320*240
Camera	200W pixels (actual use 30W), OV2640 model M12 camera
TF card slot	Multimedia resource expansion, support large-capacity storage

Source: Compiled by the author.

The platform in question was initially developed for the needs of deploying artificial intelligence on embedded systems. It has a larger set of pluggable peripherals than ESP32. Also, for working with Maix boards, Sipeed has developed the MaixPy IDE. It allows you to write code in the microPython programming language (PL). Another function is that MaixPy can display video received from the Sipeed Maix camera, as well as display its parameters.

This IDE has built-in libraries for working with the module's peripherals, which greatly simplifies the development process.

Also on the official website there is documentation for working with MaixPy, a description of its libraries and their functions. The documentation is presented in

Chinese and English. The official website has a built-in Google translator.

Pre-trained models are used to recognize objects, which must be in the kmodel or s model format. In this work, a pre-trained YOLOv2 model was used [12].

2.3 Nvidia Jetson TX2 DevKit

Nvidia Jetson TX2 DevKit is a development platform created by Nvidia, designed for developers, engineers and researchers who want to create innovative solutions using artificial intelligence (AI), deep learning and robotics.

The most promising of the presented modules, as it has significantly, tens of times, increased performance, memory and computing speed.

Table 3.

NVIDIA Jetson TX2 DevKit Parameters

Part of the module	Description
1	2
CPU	ARM8 64-bit multiprocessor with HMP CPU architecture: 64-bit dual-core NVIDIA Denver 2 processor at up to 2 GHz; Quad-core Arm® Cortex®-A57 MPCore at up to 2 GHz;
GPU	NVIDIA Pascal™ architecture with 256 NVIDIA CUDA® cores at up to 1.12GHz
Memory	4GB LPDDR4x 128-bit 1600MHz with up to 51.2Gbps bandwidth
Storage	16 GB eMMC 5.1, 128GB NVMe SSD
Screen	2 x Multi-mode DP 1.2/eDP 1.4, HDMI 2.0 2 x DSI (1.5 Gbps per channel)
Camera	Up to 5 cameras (12 via virtual channels), 12 MIPI channels CSI-2 (3x4 or 6x2), D-PHY 1.2 (up to 30 Gbps)
TF card slot	-

Source: Compiled by the author.

3. Results

The recognition device was tested on the selected embedded systems. The collected results were presented in the form of tables and graphs. This will provide a clear difference between the different stages of testing. In the case where the recognition probability is below 50 percent, we will assume that the object is not recognized, therefore, the probability is 0. The presented data is also relevant in the case where the camera

is located at a level of 90 cm and is aimed exactly at the object under study.

3.1 Nvidia Jetson TX2 DevKit

The data presented in Tables 4 - 5, as well as the data presented in Figures 1 - 6, were obtained when testing the NVIDIA Jetson TX2 DevKit module. The results obtained using the Prestigio PWC420 HD camera are presented in Table 3.

Table 4.

Test results for the Prestigio PWC420 HD camera

Camera model	Neural network model	Distance in meters	Probability of human recognition in % of illumination in lux			
			0	180	270	420
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Prestigio PWC420 HD	SSD Inception V2	2.4	< 50	90	88	89
		4.8	< 50	93	83	95
		7.2	< 50	65	64	68
		9.6	< 50	85.4	85	80
		12	< 50	< 50	< 50	< 50
		14.4	< 50	< 50	< 50	< 50
	Peoplenet-Pruned	2.4	53	99.7	99.8	99.8
		4.8	60	98.9	99	99.5
		7.2	93	98.1	97.9	94.7
		9.6	95.5	98	96	96.5
		12	95	97	97.5	98.7
		14.4	90	96.9	96.4	96
		3	4	5	6	7
		2.4	< 50	99.9	99.8	99.9
		4.8	< 50	99.8	99.8	99.8
		7.2	< 50	99.6	99.6	99.6
		9.6	< 50	97	98.3	97
		12	< 50	99.1	99.3	99.3
14.4	< 50	99.4	99.5	99.5		

Source: Compiled by the author.

The graph in Figure 1 corresponds to the measurements in Table 3 for the Inception V2 SSD model.

Fig. 1. Graph of human recognition probability using the SSD Inception V2 model

Source: Compiled by the author.

The graph in Figure 2 corresponds to the measurements in Table 3 for the Peoplenet-Pruned model.

Fig. 2. Graph of human recognition probability using the Peoplenet-Pruned model

Source: Compiled by the author.

The graph in Figure 3 corresponds to the measurements in Table 3 for the Peoplenet model.

Fig. 3. Graph of the probability of human recognition using the Peoplenet model

Source: Compiled by the author.

With the Prestigio PWC420 HD camera, the Peoplenet model showed the best result on average, except for the case with 0 lux illumination, for which the Peoplenet-Pruned model showed the best result. The results of both neural network models show a level of efficiency sufficient to achieve the goal of the study - counting the number of people in a frame in real time. At the same time, the People-pruned model requires on average 2 times less computing resources for recognition. However, in low-light conditions - 0 lux, the full-

fledged, uncut Peoplenet model was unable to recognize a person's silhouette, which its lightweight version Peoplenet-Pruned was able to do.

The results obtained using the main camera of the Samsung Galaxy A54 are presented in Table 4. The smartphone camera uses not only hardware capabilities, but also software, which improves image quality. However, this means not only a higher-quality picture, but also increased resource costs for its processing. Therefore, the application that transmits a video stream from a smartphone to the NVIDIA Jetson TX2 DevKit board reduces the image quality to 1280x720.

Table 5.

Test results for the main camera of the Samsung Galaxy A54

Camera	Neural network model	Distance in meters	Probability of human recognition in % of illumination in lux			
			0	180	270	420
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Samsung Galaxy A54 Main Camera	SSD Inception V2	2.4	99.2	< 50	99	99.3
		4.8	63	76	88	72
		7.2	< 50	< 50	< 50	< 50
		9.6	70	< 50	< 50	75
		12	< 50	< 50	< 50	< 50
		14.4	< 50	< 50	< 50	< 50
	Peoplenet-Pruned	2.4	99	99.4	99.9	99.9
		4.8	97.9	98.3	98	98.4
		7.2	98	98.7	95.4	96
		9.6	98.7	97.6	98.6	98.6
		12	97	97.5	98.8	97.3
		14.4	95.6	96	95.7	96.5
	Peoplenet	2.4	99.9	99.9	99.9	99.9
		4.8	98	98.9	98.5	98.9
		7.2	99.4	99	99.2	99.6
		9.6	97	99.5	98.6	98.6
		12	98	98	99.2	99.5
		14.4	98	98	96	99.3

Source: Compiled by the author.

The graph in Figure 4 corresponds to the measurements in Table 4 for the SSD Inception V2 model. The graph in Figure 5 corresponds to the measurements in Table 4 for the Peoplenet-Pruned model. The graph in Figure 6 corresponds to the measurements in Table 4 for the Peoplenet model.

Fig. 4. Graph of human recognition probability using the SSD Inception V2 model

Source: Compiled by the author.

Fig. 5. Graph of the probability of human recognition using the Peoplenet-Pruned model

Source: Compiled by the author.

Fig. 6. Graph of the probability of human recognition using the Peoplenet model

Source: Compiled by the author.

For the main camera of the Samsung A54 smartphone, the Peoplenet model showed the best result. At the same time, the Peoplenet-pruned model shows an average efficiency of 1% less, but which remains at a level sufficient to perform the task.

3.2. Sipeed Maix Bit

The data presented in Table 6, as well as the data presented in Figure 7, were obtained during testing of

the Sipeed Maix Bit module. This module is based on the K210 chip, for which there are not many models to use. The tests were conducted using the YOLO V2 neural network model [13]. It is also possible to train your own model for specific needs on the official Maix website [14]. However, the models trained using the proposed tool are not accurate enough to be used in general tests, as the accuracy was less than 60% at best [15].

Table 6.

Test results for Sipeed Maix Bit

Camera	Neural network model	Distance in meters	Probability of human recognition in % of illumination in lux			
			0	180	270	420
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
OV2640	YOLO V2	2.4	< 50	98	99	99
		4.8	< 50	96	96	97
		7.2	< 50	91	91	96
		9.6	< 50	73	62	64
		12	< 50	< 50	< 50	< 50
		14.4	< 50	< 50	< 50	< 50

Source: Compiled by the author.

The graph in Figure 7 corresponds to the measurements from Table 6 for the YOLO V2 model.

Fig. 7. Graph of the probability of human recognition using the YOLO V2 model

Source: Compiled by the author.

It is not possible to conduct a comparative analysis of the performance of different models for this platform, since it was not possible to select a larger number of models for testing.

Conclusion

When using NVIDIA Jetson TX2 DevKit, the Peoplenet model showed the best results for both cameras. The main difference is that the smartphone camera automatically adjusts the camera's light sensitivity. This allows it to recognize objects in low-light areas. The Peoplenet-pruned model showed results close to the unpruned Peoplenet model, but, on average, consumed half as many resources. SSD-Inception-v3 showed the worst result. Regardless of the distance, instability in the model's results was observed, and when the object reached a distance of 12 meters from the image source, the ability to recognize was completely lost.

As with the SSD Inception V2 and Peoplenet models with the Prestigio PWC420 HD camera, with insufficient illumination, the module is unable to recognize an object at the entire sample of distances. However, unlike the NVIDIA Jetson TX2 DevKit with the Inception V2 SSD and the Prestigio PWC420 HD camera, the Sipeed Maix Bit with the Yolo V2 showed greater linearity when changing illumination and distance.

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